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COMPREHENSIVE OVERVIEW ON MUCORMYCOSIS WITH RECENT ADVANCEMENT IN TREATMENT

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ABSTRACT

Mucormycosis is a life-threatening infection caused by the fungus Mucorales belonging to zygomycetes class. In India in 2021 it has become an epidemic in midst of the covid -19 pandemic, Mucormycosis is causing high mortality in patients with underlying predisposing risk factors like diabetes mellitus, hematological malignancy, transplantation, immunocompromised individuals and covid associated mucormycosis is seen in patients treated with concurrent glucocorticoid therapy. This infection is non communicable, so it does not spread from one person to another. Early diagnosis and early initiation of treatment is required for preventing further spread of the disease and death. This infection is difficult to diagnose as the symptoms shown overlaps with many other known infections. Management therapy includes treatment with antifungal medications and surgical debridement of the infected necrotic tissue. Prevention of the infection is possible only by the management of underlying risk factors like by better control of diabetes, restricted use of glucocorticoids, antibiotics.

Keywords:

Mucormycosis, black fungus, mucorales, zygomycosis

INTRODUCTION

Mucormycosis earlier known as zygomycosis is a rare but serious life-threatening angioinvasive infection caused by filamentous moulds belonging to the class zygomycete within the order mucorales [1][2][3][4]

Glucocorticoid therapy for coronavirus increases the risk of mucormycosis [5]. Other risk factors include uncontrolled diabetes mellitus, hematological malignancies like lymphomas and leukemia, autoimmune disease, chronic renal failure, malnutrition, organ transplant, burns, immunosuppressive therapy, cirrhosis, AIDS and mostly immunocompromised patients and diabetic ketoacidosis and patients on dialysis with iron chelator deferoxamine are also more susceptible to mucormycosis [6]. Mode of transmission of mucormycosis is through inhalation of spores of fungal conidia directly into the lungs, inoculation through disrupted skin, ingestion of contaminated food [7]

Types of Mucormycosis [3] [8]

Rhino-orbital cerebral: Mucormycosis is an infection which affects the sinus and brain mostly seen in patients with uncontrolled diabetes and patients underwent transplant.

- **Pulmonary mucormycosis:** Mostly seen in people with cancer and organ transplant /stem cell transplant
- **Gastrointestinal mucormycosis:** Seen in premature neonates with low birth weight, malnourished children, and patients with hematological malignancy, diabetes mellitus has undergone surgery.
- **Cutaneous mucormycosis:** It occurs through a break in the skin especially through a burn, skin trauma.
- **Disseminated mucormycosis:** Commonly spreads infection through the bloodstream affecting the brain, , spleen, skin, heart.

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Aetiology

Mucormycosis is a life-threatening infectious disease caused mainly by a group of fungi belonging to *Rhizopus oryzae* species other causative organisms include *mucor*, *cunninghamella*, *apophysomyces*, *Lichtheimia*, *Saksenaea*, *Rhizomucor* and 70% of all cases of mucormycosis cases reported is caused by *Rhizopus oryzae*[9].

Epidemiology

Mucormycosis occurs mainly through the inhalation of fungal spores released in the air or direct inoculation of spores through broken skin and mucosa. The infection is usually uncommon in developed countries but likely to be seen in immunocompromised patients and patients with uncontrolled diabetes mellitus(3) and recently during the covid 19 pandemics it was diagnosed in patients with covid 19 who were under glucocorticoid therapy and people with viral-induced lymphopenia developed mucormycosis[10]. In India more than 4300 patients have died of mucormycosis during the covid -19 pandemic, 45374 cases have been reported in India till July 2021[11]

Symptoms

Fever, facial pain, eye pain, toothache, paraesthesia, blurred vision, blackish discolouration of the skin, nasal congestion with headache, nausea, vomiting, stomach pain, GIT bleeding[12]

Diagnosis

Diagnosis of mucormycosis is quite challenging direct microscopy of clinical specimens can be used for the diagnosis, microscopic view can be done with wet mounting techniques, periodic acid Schiff stain, fluorescent in-situ hybridization. Even molecular-based techniques like conventional PCR, DNA Sequencing, and Real-time PCR are used for diagnosis. CT scan can be used to determine the exact location and spread of infection[13].

Treatment

The treatment procedure of mucormycosis involves early diagnosis of the infection, reversing the underlying, reversing the underlying predisposing risk factors like uncontrolled diabetes mellitus and the administration of antifungal therapy which may be monotherapy or combination therapy and surgical debridement of the affected necrotic tissues.

The initial first-line treatment is with liposomal amphotericin B, posaconazole or isavuconazole is given to patients as a step-down therapy who may have responded to amphotericin B and as salvage therapy who don't respond to amphotericin B. Sometimes use of hyperbaric oxygen therapy is used which is like exposing the patients to pure and 100% oxygen in a pressure room of 2 to 2.5 atmosphere for about 90 to 120 minutes given every 12 hrs to 24 hrs[14].

Conclusion

Mucormycosis is an opportunistic, highly invasive and fatal fungal infection. Drugs like amphotericin B and isavuconazole is used as a first line treatment and the antifungal drug posaconazole is used as a salvage treatment. Early diagnosis with proper initiation of drug therapy is needed for the proper management of the disease. A continuous preclinical study and clinical research is needed for the development of promising treatment strategies.

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